

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Obtaining Informed Consent from Study Subjects

Use Case

Bente Miller is investigating the verbal behavior of twelve-year-olds and would like to conduct interviews with children in this age group. Bente Miller wants to analyze the data in this research project and then use them in an anonymized form in publications. Bente Miller would also like to have the possibility to use the data for follow-up projects, perhaps even the original recordings.

Bente Miller is wondering which of these purposes require informed consent and what needs to be taken into account when obtaining consent.

When do you (not) need informed consent?

As soon as personal data are collected for research purposes, researchers must inform the individuals concerned and, if necessary, obtain their [consent](#). This is in line with good scientific practice, contributes to transparency, and, last but not least, provides legal protection for researchers. Whether obtaining informed consent is legally required depends on the individual case and the applicable law. It is therefore always advisable to obtain informed consent when you are conducting research with personal data and to discuss how to do so with legal services or the university's data-protection officer beforehand.

If data are collected anonymously, that is, in such a way that no conclusions can be drawn about the individuals concerned, consent is not required.

Furthermore, consent is not required for processing data that does not have a personal reference (so-called research privilege). This means that it is not required to obtain consent from the individuals concerned when data that had a personal reference and were collected

for a specific purpose are reused for another purpose in an anonymized or pseudonymized form. Here is an example: A canton collects personal tax data for the purpose of tax collection. These data may be made available in an anonymized or pseudonymized form for statistical research purposes. It is not required to obtain the taxpayers' consent for the statistical analysis.

The anonymization or pseudonymization must be carried out as soon as the processing purpose allows. And it goes without saying that any research results may only be published in an anonymized form.

A further exception may apply to [public figures](#).

What should an informed-consent document contain in order to cover all the usage scenarios during and after a project?

An informed-consent document must in principle contain precise information about the purpose for processing the personal data. An informed-consent document that only describes the purpose in general terms—for example, «for research purposes»—is not sufficient. Furthermore, the consent document must also cover all the working steps of the respective research project, from data collection, analysis, and the publication of results to the archiving of raw data and the possible deletion of data. [If data processing will be contracted out to third parties](#), this must also be specified in the consent document. And if the collected data might also be used for purposes other than the described research purpose—for example, for other research projects, [teaching, or presentations at conferences](#)—the consent document must also include them specifically.

Who must or who can give consent?

In principle, the individuals concerned must always give their consent.

Consent can be given by anyone who is capable of making their own decisions, that is, by anyone who can act rationally. Minors may also be capable of making their own decisions depending on their age and the context. This must always be determined on a case-by-case basis. With regard to children, the decisive factor is whether they can grasp and understand the specific data processing and assess the resulting consequences. As it is difficult to judge children's capacity for making their own decisions, it always makes sense to inform their legal guardians and obtain their consent.

How do you have to formulate the informed-consent document?

It is important that the consent document is formulated in such a way that it is understandable for the individuals concerned—in the above example, including for children. The data subjects must understand what they are consenting to and what will happen to their data. Legal or technical language should therefore be avoided as much as possible.

Does consent always have to be given in writing?

The form in which consent may be given is governed by the applicable law. For reasons of proof, however, a written form of consent is always recommended. In the event that consent can only be given verbally, care should nevertheless be taken to ensure that it and the information are recorded. This can be done, for instance, by means of an audio recording. This is also one way to obtain valid consent from people who are unable to read or write.

Is it possible to obtain consent retrospectively after data have been collected?

In principle, consent must always be given prior to the processing of personal data. Since collecting data already belongs to data processing in the legal sense, consent must already be given before collecting data.

Tips on informed-consent documents

Multitiered consent

It may be sensible to structure a consent document in multiple tiers so that the data subjects have the option of selectively consenting to different uses of the data. For example, people may be happy to allow their data to be used for a research project but do not want the material to be published. The advantage of this approach is that someone does not have to withhold their consent for all the uses.

Publication

If research data are published on a repository, the metadata should indicate what type of consent was obtained. This allows other researchers to see whether or how they may reuse the data should the occasion arise.

What does that mean for this case?

Before interviewing the twelve-year-olds, Bente Miller obtains informed consent from the children and their legal guardians to conduct the interviews, to use them for the research project, and to publish the results. Bente Miller informs the individuals concerned and their parents that the resulting data may be used in an anonymized form for further research purposes. In addition, Bente Miller asks for another optional consent to store the respondents' contact details for five years after the end of the research project so as to be able to contact the individuals concerned to obtain their consent to use the nonanonymized data for a second project. Around half of the respondents agree to this.